

Robomat Project: attracting young students to STEM areas

Lílian Barros Pereira Campos¹, Dair José de Oliveira¹, Marli Cristina Ferreira², João Paulo Roquim Romanelli¹, Rosa Ferreira Da Silva³

¹ Federal University of Itajubá - Theodomiro Santiago Campos - Itabira - Minas Gerais - Brazil

² Fazenda Betânia State High School

³ Trajano Procópio State High School

Email: liliancampos@unifei.edu.br, dairoliveira@unifei.edu.br, marli.cristina@educacao.mg.gov.br, joaoromanelli@unifei.edu.br, rosa.ferreira.silva@educacao.mg.gov.br,

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15847118>

Abstract

In Brazil, innovating in public basic education presents significant challenges, particularly when undertaken in contexts characterized by limited resources, low levels of teacher motivation, and complex social conditions—including vulnerability, violence, and exposure to drug-related environments—which may constrain the implementation and sustainability of innovative practices. Attracting students from public schools to higher education, especially in STEM fields, is difficult, with mathematics often intimidating potential candidates. To address this, the Federal University of Itajubá is conducting the "Educational Robotics and Mathematical Thinking" (ROBOMAT) project that is funded by the Foundation for Research Support of Minas Gerais (FAPEMIG). Its primary goal is to introduce the university as a professional training option for students from two public schools in Itabira, Minas Gerais. In this project, 20 students participate in weekly activities at the university. The project activities are facilitated by students from the Drummonsters robotics team. These activities are designed to develop competencies in electronics, mechanics, and programming, as well as transversal competencies such as creativity, communication, resilience, and collaboration. This paper outlines the project's objectives and learning dynamics. To assess the project's impact, data from two data collections are presented. The first data collection, conducted before the project started (May 2024), identified students' expectations and interest in STEM fields, while the second data collection, conducted in December 2024, gathered students' perceptions of their learning after a six-month activities project. Deliverables involved creating a program on the Scratch app that demonstrated mathematical knowledge were analysed in this context. The data analysis revealed key challenges, including motivating students despite external pressures and developing competencies that are unfamiliar to them. So, this paper presents the main challenges of a project that aims to inspire students to pursue higher education and STEM fields by fostering both technical and transversal competencies, while addressing barriers within public education.

Keywords: Active Learning; secondary education; robotics, STEM.

1 Introduction

According to the Brazilian Curriculum Guidelines for High School, issued by the Secretariat of Basic Education of the Brazilian Ministry of Education, the quality of schools is an essential condition for inclusion and the democratization of opportunities in Brazil. Based on this understanding, the challenge of providing quality basic education to support student inclusion, national development, and the consolidation of citizenship is a task for all (MEC, 2006).

In this context, one way universities can contribute to addressing this issue is by acting as catalysts through extension activities that help students expand their knowledge and skills, while also encouraging them to view higher education as a viable path for their future. When such projects take place within the field of Engineering, multiple outcomes can be achieved through the interaction between the academic community and high school students, such as the development of individuals, the dissemination of technology, and the encouragement of young people's interest in STEM (science, technology, engineering, and math) careers (Bacich & Holanda, 2020).

With this in mind, professors from the Federal University of Itajubá – Itabira campus created the project Educational Robotics and Mathematical Thinking in Basic Education, aimed at fostering interaction between faculty and students from the Federal University of Itajubá – Itabira campus and students from two public high schools in Itabira: Escola Estadual Trajano Procópio Alvarenga Silva Monteiro (PREMEM) and Escola Estadual da Fazenda Betânia (EEFB). The project's main goal is to develop STEM-related skills among high school students. This initiative is funded by the Minas Gerais Research Support Foundation (FAPEMIG) under Call 14/2023, with an expected duration from May 2024 to May 2027.

To assess the project's impact, data from two collection phases are presented. The first data collection took place in May 2024, before the project started, through a survey designed to identify students' expectations and interest in STEM fields such as educational robotics, mathematical thinking, engineering, and STEM-related careers. This survey was conducted using physical questionnaires administered to 101 first-year high school students from the two participating schools. The second data collection occurred in December 2024 and aimed to capture students' perceptions of their learning progress up to that point in the project. Additionally, students' reports on a programming challenge were analyzed to assess their competencies in programming, mathematical thinking, and transversal skills such as creativity, collaboration, and communication.

This paper is organized into seven sections. The first section introduces the context and objectives of the paper. Section two discusses the integration of educational robotics and mathematical thinking in Brazilian basic education. Section three presents the study context. Section four presents the materials and methods used. The fifth section presents the results and discussion. The sixth section draws some conclusions. The last section presents the references used in this study.

2 Educational Robotics and Mathematical Thinking in Basic Education

In the context of this paper, the integration of Educational Robotics and mathematical thinking in Basic Education is highly beneficial. When robotics is used for educational purposes, it is referred to as Educational Robotics (ER) (Barbosa et al., 2015). ER is considered a process that extends far beyond the mere assembly of parts, as it fosters changes in attitude, dialogue, cooperation, methodology, questioning, and inquiry among teachers and students, as well as the construction of meaning (Barbosa et al., 2015). In this context, the robot serves as a tool that allows teachers to practically demonstrate complex theoretical concepts—sometimes difficult to grasp—while also motivating students, who are constantly challenged to observe, abstract, and innovate (Barbosa et al., 2015).

Additionally, considering D'Ambrosio's (1996) perspective on reality construction, mathematical thinking can be understood as an essential cognitive ability that emerges from the human need to comprehend, structure, and transform reality. In this view, mathematical thinking is more than just the manipulation of numbers and symbols; it represents a dynamic process of abstraction and logical reasoning, enabling the creation of models, the identification of patterns, and the resolution of complex problems (Pessoa, 2024). For this reason, mathematical thinking is not confined to the use of digits; rather, it permeates all fields of knowledge and daily life, functioning as a tool for both survival and innovation. This broad perspective of mathematical thinking highlights how individuals process information from reality and act upon it, generating a continuous cycle of action and influence that drives change and discoveries beyond their existence (D'Ambrosio, 1996; Pessoa, 2024). In this way, mathematical thinking is not only fundamental in the process of understanding and explaining the world but also enables individuals to transform it, playing a fundamental role in the advancement of science, technology, and human development (D'Ambrosio, 1996; Ellenberg, 2015; Pessoa, 2024).

In this sense, educational robotics and mathematical thinking can be connected, as both promote problem-solving, logical reasoning, and creativity in the learning process. While mathematical thinking provides a foundation for abstraction, pattern recognition, and structured reasoning (Pessoa, 2024), educational robotics serves as an attractive practical application of these cognitive skills, allowing students to experiment, test hypotheses, and refine their understanding through hands-on activities (Barbosa et al., 2015).

This approach is aligned with Brazilian Curriculum Guidelines for High School (MEC, 2006) which recommends that by the end of high school, students are expected to know how to use Mathematics to solve practical problems and to understand the importance of Mathematics for scientific and technological development. In this regard, skills such as problem-solving, critical thinking, communication of ideas, and cooperation need to be developed for the full education of the student (Oliveira, Siqueira, and Romão, 2020) and robotics education can be an effective strategy.

As an example of the integration of educational robotics and mathematical thinking in Brazilian basic education, Da Silveira, Coelho, and Santos (2017) present a teaching experience in Mathematics through the use of a low-cost robot based on the Arduino architecture, with open hardware and software, to work on first-degree functions. Among the proposed activities, students were required to program the robot, check the execution, analyze its behavior, correct errors, and conduct new tests to carry out the proposed tasks. According to the authors, students were active in the knowledge-building process, presenting different levels of difficulty, some of which were related to their lack of familiarity with how robots operate.

Nevertheless, it is important to emphasize that such approaches aim to integrate mathematical thinking with the solution of real dilemmas or more concrete challenges. Seeking this integration of knowledge is considered one of the ways to improve the quality of basic education through increased student engagement, enhanced performance, and mathematical learning (Santos, 2018). It is important to note that teaching strategies are only one of the variables in the teaching-learning process, as the challenges in basic education also involve social and economic aspects (Campos et al, 2024).

3 Study Context

This paper is a product of a study within the scope of the Educational Robotics and Mathematical Thinking in Education project at the Federal University of Itajubá – Itabira campus. This project involves 20 students from two public high schools in the city of Itabira, Minas Gerais State in Brazil: Escola Estadual Trajano Procópio Alvarenga Silva Monteiro (PREMEM) and Escola Estadual da Fazenda Betânia (EEFB).

The project addressed these high schools for some reasons. First, the impact the project can have in terms of representativeness in the municipality and the results for the development of students directly and indirectly involved in the project. The total number of students enrolled in these two schools accounts for 51% of the high school enrollment in Itabira. Secondly, according to data from the Basic Education Evaluation System (SAEB), both schools show unfavorable math learning indicators. At PREMEM, in 2019, 46% of students demonstrated adequate math learning. Considering the Target 3 of the Todos Pela Educação initiative, which states that 70% of students should demonstrate adequate learning, this indicator suggests failure, as less than 50% of students show adequate learning. At this school, the average Brazilian High School Exam (ENEM) score was 542.60, and 60% of graduates took the exam in 2019. ENEM is a nationwide standardized exam used for university admission in Brazil.

Additionally, the situation at EEFB is even more critical. In 2019, only 3% of students demonstrated adequate math learning. This indicates a severe situation and points to the social barriers faced by the community where the school is located. At this school, the average ENEM score was 461.53, and only 26% of graduates took the

exam in 2019. These data highlight the need to support these schools in the critical challenge of providing adequate learning. The project proposal is based on the hypothesis that the initiative can help students develop mathematical thinking to the point of positively impacting the learning indicators set by SAEB.

The project management team consists of three professors from Unifei: an Electrical Engineer, a Mathematician, and an Administrator. Additionally, two high school teachers are involved—one specializing in Biology and the other in Science. The project execution team includes six graduate students selected to work as facilitators, responsible for teaching programming, electronics, and mechanics, which are the core areas of robotics that high school students need to learn.

At the project's inception, it was decided that only 20 first-year high school students could participate due to space limitations in the laboratory where the activities take place. As a recruitment strategy, the management team visited the high schools, briefly introduced the project, and collected data on students' expectations and interest in STEM fields. To select participants, a mathematics test was administered. However, in both schools, only five students took the test, indicating a lower-than-expected level of interest in the project. To fill the remaining spots, the management team accepted an additional five students from each school who expressed a desire to participate, even though they were in their second year of high school.

Project activities began in May 2024. Since then, high school students have attended weekly sessions at the university, where the students are exposed to a combination of content from the regular high school curriculum and new, robotics-specific knowledge. The central objective of the first semester of the program was the development of a line-following robot, a challenge that is a practical application of the theoretical concepts learned. In this sense, the initiative learning objective is to equip them with the knowledge and skills necessary to develop simple robotic solutions to address real-world problems. Table 1 presents the lesson planning for the first semester of the project.

Table 1 - Lesson Planning for the First Semester

Content	Competency
Line Follower	Understand and be able to develop the initial concept of the line follower.
Electrochemistry	Describe the functioning of a battery and its configurations.
Measurement Units and Ohm's Law	Understand the importance of measurement units. Explain the relationships between electrical quantities such as voltage, current, and resistance.
Motor, H-Bridge, Sensor, Battery	Be able to specify a motor, an H-Bridge, a battery, and sensors for a line follower.
Light Propagation and Reflection	Understand the basic concepts of light and the operating principle of sensors used in a line follower robot.
Programming	Understand the concept of algorithms, logical and mathematical operations, and data input and output.
Introduction to the ESP32 Microcontroller	Understand the basic characteristics and applications of the ESP32, including its programming and communication interfaces.
Prototype Assembly	Assemble the mechanical components and electronic circuit of the line follower.
Project Adjustments	Optimize parameters to reduce the lap time of the line follower.
Competition	Interact with peers and exchange experiences between teams.

4 Materials and Method

This paper presents the report of two data collection phases. The first phase took place prior to the start of the project activities, and the second one occurred five months into the project. In the initial phase, an exploratory survey was conducted (GIL, 2002). A total of 101 first-year students from high schools in Itabira participated in this phase, including 71 students from PREMEM and 30 from EEFB. In the second phase, 8 students from

PREMEM and 2 from EEFB were involved. This phase also included a qualitative analysis of students' reports on a programming challenge, which required them to apply both math and programming knowledge. From these reports, insights were gained into students' perceptions of their learning progress throughout the project. Table 2 shows the number of students involved in the data collection phases of this study.

Table 2. Number of students per data collection phase

Data collection phase	Date	PREMEM Students	EEFB Students
Expectations and interest in STEM fields	May 2024	71	30
Perceptions of their learning progress	December 2024	8	2

In the first part of data collection, the objective was to identify students' expectations regarding the project, as well as their level of interest in educational robotics, mathematical thinking, and STEM-related careers. Data were collected using physical questionnaires administered to first-year high school students from both participating schools. The questionnaire consisted of five questions. The first three gathered demographic information, including identification, gender, and age. Question four asked students to indicate their level of interest in three areas: a) STEM fields (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics); b) participation in projects involving robotics and robotics combined with mathematical thinking; and c) future academic aspirations, such as enrolling in technical education, taking ENEM exam, and studying at Unifei (the university where the project is executed). To answer these questions, a five-point Likert scale was used, where 1 represented no interest and 5 represented high interest. Question five asked students to list their preferred professions. The questionnaire was administered during a visit to the schools after a brief presentation by the project team. No specific details about the project's execution were shared to ensure that students' responses remained unbiased by prior information.

In the second part of data collection, students were asked to write a report about a programming challenge they participated in. This challenge was called Digital Safe in Scratch Platform. The object of the challenge was to engage students in programming and logical reasoning by having them create a password validation system. In the first phase, each student individually defined three custom rules for a three-digit code and implemented them in Scratch Platform, using variables and conditional statements. It was expected that the program prompted the user to input numbers, to check if they met the rules, and to display whether the password was valid or invalid. In the second phase, students paired up to test each other's programs by attempting to bypass the rules and then collaborated to create a more complex digital safe with a four-digit code and challenging new rules. After implementing the new program, the pairs presented their solutions, explained their reasoning, and challenged their peers to crack the code. This challenge aimed to foster creativity, problem-solving, and teamwork while promoting computational thinking.

The student reports were analyzed to identify their perceptions of learning and progress up to the fifth month of the project.

5 Results and discussion

The characterization of the students who responded to the first data collection is presented in Table 3. In this sample, 56% were male, 43% were female, and 1 person self-identified as another gender, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3 - Demographic characterization of the surveyed students - gender

Gender	Quantity of students	Percent
Female	43	43%
Male	57	56%
Other	1	1%

Regarding the students' age, 87 students were in the 15 to 16-year-old range, while the remaining students were in the 17 to 18-year-old range (Table 4).

Table 4 - Demographic characterization of the surveyed students - age range

Age range	Quantity of students	Percent
15-16	87	86%
17-18	14	14%

To analyze the students' areas of interest, the percentage of students with high interest in the topics surveyed is tabulated below, meaning students who answered 4 or 5 on the proposed interest scale. The students were asked about their interest in STEM fields: science, technology, engineering, and mathematics. Regarding technology interest, two questions were posed: one about interest in using technology and another about interest in learning how to develop technology. As shown in Figure 1, 84% of students reported a high interest in using technology, while 78% expressed interest in learning to develop technology. It is worth noting that the 6 percentage point difference between these two perceptions regarding technology in this sample highlights the particularity of Generation Z, who, as digital natives, make intensive use of technology but do not necessarily have an interest in engaging in technological development.

Figure 1: Percentage chart of students with high interest in STEM fields.

In descending order, the interest in sciences (47%), engineering (41%), and mathematics (31%) was observed. This scenario reflects the Brazilian reality of a growing disinterest in exact sciences, highlighting the need for actions to promote and value these areas of knowledge, which are crucial for the future of work (IFTF, 2017; UNESCO, 2018; Neto & Batista, 2020; Foschaches et al., 2023).

To assess students' interest in the specific field of robotics, they were asked about their willingness to participate in two types of projects. The first involved robotics, and the second combined robotics with mathematical thinking. As shown in Figure 2, 35% of students expressed high interest in robotics, while 48% showed interest in participating in projects on this topic. Regarding the option of participating in a project involving both robotics and mathematical thinking, 30% of students expressed high interest.

Figure 2: Percentage of students with high interest in a robotics project, robotics and robotics and math projects.

This result may indicate students' aversion or even fear towards mathematics, considering this area of knowledge as difficult and unpleasant (Prediger, Berwanger & Mörs, 2013). This reality points to the need to present mathematics in a way that is connected to the student's reality, using areas of their interest, so that this field of knowledge becomes relevant for solving issues that are meaningful to the student.

Regarding expectations for continuing their studies, students were asked about their intentions to enroll in a technical course, take the ENEM, and study at Unifei. Figure 3 shows the responses to these questions. 78% of the students expressed interest in pursuing a technical course, 67% expressed interest in studying at Unifei, and 60% reported interest in taking the ENEM.

Figure 3: Percentage of students with high interest in taking a technical course, taking ENEM, and studying at Unifei

When asked about their specific interest in participating in the Educational Robotics and Mathematical Thinking project, 47% of the students said yes. Of this group, 21 students were female, 26 were male, and 1 self-identified as another gender.

To complement the understanding of the students' professional plans, they were asked which professions they were interested in. To represent the responses, a word cloud was created, shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Word cloud with interesting professions mentioned by the students

The analysis of the students' responses regarding their career interests revealed a diverse range of aspirations, with a strong emphasis on STEM-related fields. Professions such as engineering, medicine, computer programming, and biotechnology appeared frequently, indicating a significant level of interest in technical and scientific areas. Additionally, careers in law and biomedical science were also commonly mentioned, reflecting a blend of both human sciences and business-oriented interests. The presence of creative and less conventional roles like YouTuber, pilot, and illustrator suggests that students are also exploring modern and dynamic career paths influenced by current technological and cultural trends.

In the second phase of data collection, 5 student reports were analysed. Table 5 summarizes some characteristics of these reports.

Table 5 - Student's reports characteristics - quality and content

#	Reports Quality	Content	High School
Report 1	This report was well-written and effectively highlighted the opportunities students had to enhance their programming and problem-solving skills.	Challenge description and declaration of knowledge access during the learning activity (mathematics thinking and programming)	PREMEM
Report 2	The report was overly simplistic, lacked proper formatting, and it presented the content in a superficial manner.	The students highlighted that they use factorials, multiplication, and division. They reported that completing the challenge was difficult and they expressed gratitude for the opportunity to participate in a highly valuable experience	EEFB
Report 3	The report was overly simplistic, lacked proper formatting, and it presented the content in a superficial manner.	Challenge description and explanation of reasoning they got in the challenge.	PREMEM
Report 4	This report was well-written and effectively highlighted the opportunities students had to enhance their programming and problem-solving skills.	Challenge description and declaration of knowledge access during the learning activity (mathematics thinking, programming, creativity and logical thinking).	PREMEM
Report 5	This report was well-written and effectively highlighted the opportunities students had to enhance their programming and problem-solving skills.	The report mentioned the opportunity to explore an area of innovative development, offering different perspectives on the technology and how it impacts everyday contexts.	PREMEM

The five student reports varied in quality. Some students, particularly from PREMEM, demonstrated stronger writing skills by clearly describing the challenge, its development process, and the key learning outcomes. On the other hand, all reports highlighted not only elements of mathematical thinking but also the transversal skills that were engaged throughout the challenge. As the students highlighted these learning outcomes, it can be inferred that the project has been effective in integrating mathematical thinking and programming skills. Given that the project has been running for only six months, it is crucial to continue monitoring its results to assess its long-term impact on participants' knowledge.

6 Conclusions

The data from this study on the Educational Robotics and Mathematical Thinking Project reveal both the potential and challenges of engaging high school students in STEM-related extracurricular activities. Despite an initial recruitment of 101 first-year high school students, only 47 expressed interest in participating and 10 enrolled in the selection phase. Since the project management team decided to offer 20 spots, an additional 10 second-year high school students who expressed interest in the project were admitted. However, only 10 were present at the programming challenge proposed six months into the project. These facts illustrate the significant challenge of maintaining student engagement in projects driven solely by intrinsic motivation, without financial incentives.

The findings also indicate a high interest in using technology (84%) and developing it (78%), although interest declines in fields like science (47%), engineering (41%), and mathematics (31%). This gap underscores a broader societal trend of disengagement from mathematics and exact sciences in Brazil. Moreover, while 35% of students showed interest in robotics, only 30% were eager to engage in projects combining robotics with mathematical thinking, suggesting potential apprehension toward mathematics. The varied career aspirations—ranging from STEM fields to creative and modern roles—highlight the diverse interests of Generation Z and the need for adaptable, interest-driven educational approaches.

Despite the limited number of students who participated in the proposed challenge, all the reports analyzed showed the integration of mathematical thinking and knowledge related to robotics. It is also noticeable that all the reports mention transversal competencies that students recognize as being developed during the project, such as logical reasoning, creativity, and collaboration.

Research limitations include the small sample size that reached the final stages of the project, potential self-selection bias, and limited longitudinal data to assess long-term impact. Additionally, the analysis of only five student reports restricts broader generalizations about learning outcomes. Future research should explore strategies to enhance student motivation, perhaps through incentives or stronger integration with formal education. Longitudinal studies with larger, more diverse cohorts are also needed to assess sustained impact and refine approaches to presenting mathematics in ways that resonate with students' realities and interests.

References

- Bacich, L., & Holanda, L. (2020). STEAM em sala de aula: a aprendizagem baseada em projetos integrando conhecimentos na educação básica. Penso Editora, 2020.
- Barbosa, F. da C.; Alexandre, M. L.; Alves, D. B.; Menezes, D. C. de; Campos, G. L.; Nakamura, Y. S. N.; S. Junior, A. J. de; Lopes, C. R. (2015). Robótica Educacional em Prol do Ensino de Matemática. In: Workshop de Informática na Escola (WIE), 21. , 2015, Maceió. Proceedings [...]. Porto Alegre: Sociedade Brasileira de Computação. p. 271-280. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5753/cbie.wie.2015.271>.
- Campos, L. B. P., Oliveira, D. J. de, Ferreira, M. C., Romanelli, J. P. R., Silva, R. F. da. (2024). Robótica educacional e pensamento matemático: uma análise sobre o interesse de estudantes do ensino médio para as áreas STEM. In: Congresso Brasileiro de Educação em Engenharia (COBENGE). doi: 10.37702/2175-957X.COBENGE.2024.5233
- D'Ambrosio, U. (1996) Educação matemática: da teoria à prática. 17. ed. Campinas, SP: Papirus.
- Ellenberg, J. (2015). O poder do pensamento matemático: a ciência de como não estar errado. Editora Schwarcz-Companhia das Letras.

- Foscaches, N.; De Mari, D.; Fabris, T.; Holpert, C.; Peral, P.. (2023). Meninas brasileiras e inserção em STEAM: Abismo no presente e horizonte para um novo futuro. In: I Congresso Internacional de Mulheres em STEAM, [S. l.], v. 1, n. 1, 2023. doi: 10.55592/ICIMESTEAM.2022.4947127.
- Gil, A. C. (2002). Como elaborar projetos de pesquisa (Vol. 4, p. 175). São Paulo: Atlas.
- ITF INTITUTE FOR THE FUTURE (2017). The next era of human|machine partnerships. Emerging Technologies' Impact on Society & Work in 2030. https://www.delltechnologies.com/content/dam/delltechnologies/assets/perspectives/2030/pdf/SR1940_IFTFforDellTechnologies_Human-Machine_070517_readerhigh-res.pdf.
- Ministério da Educação (2006). Secretaria de Educação Básica. Orientações Curriculares para o Ensino Médio: Ciências da natureza, matemática e suas tecnologias. Volume 2. Brasília, https://portal.mec.gov.br/seb/arquivos/pdf/book_volume_02_internet.pdf
- Neto, V.; Batista, R. (2020). Problematizando a Agenda da Educação 2030: Relatório da UNESCO, Relações de Gênero, Educação STEM e Direitos Humanos. Revista de Educação Matemática, [s. l.], v. 17, p. e020057, 2020. doi: 10.37001/remat25269062v17id466. <https://www.revistasbemsp.com.br/index.php/REMat-SP/article/view/175>.
- Pessoa, Â. P. D. S. (2024). O pensamento matemático no ensino médio integrado: uma iniciativa educativa para a formação politécnica. [Master thesis, Programa de Pós-Graduação em Educação Profissional e Tecnológica (ProfEPT) Instituto Federal do Amazonas, https://bdtd.ibict.br/vufind/Record/IFAM-1_9b36db95e87c8d5e3a3cf20ae7aec631#details]
- Santos, M. L. da S. F. de S. (2018). Aprendizagem baseada em projetos aplicada no ensino de matemática do ensino médio. (Master's thesis, Mestrado em Ciências. Escola de Engenharia de Lorena. Universidade de São Paulo). <https://teses.usp.br/teses/disponiveis/97/97138/tde-04122018-144354/pt-br.php>.
- UNESCO. (2018) Decifrar o código: educação de meninas e mulheres em ciência, tecnologia, e engenharia e matemática (STEM). Organização das Nações Unidas para a Educação, a Ciência e a Cultura, 7, place de Fontenoy, 75352 Paris 07 SP, França, e pela Representação da UNESCO no Brasil. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000264691>.